

Feedback from Workshop 5:

Systematisation of Experience

Intensive case study: Opening nature and the outdoors to Black, Asian and Ethnic Minority communities.¹

Saturday 22nd March (with optional walk on 23rd March) at Mercure Thame Lambert hotel, Oxfordshire, UK.

From Coventry University (CU): Geraldine Brown (GB), Alex Franklin (AF), Barbara Smith (BS), Lindy Binder (LB)

From Dadima’s CIC (DC): Geeta Ludhra (GL), Subash Ludhra (SL), plus 10 participants (Learning Community members) who have attended Dadima’s walks.

Agenda: PLANET4B UK Case Study – Learning Community Workshop 5

Time	Item	Lead(s)
08.30	Pre-meeting for facilitators and Dadima’s, SL & GL	
09.00	Arrival Coffee and Pastries	
09.30	Morning session: welcome and introduction Priya – Using Oils to Stimulate Memories Connecting (5 minutes – talking to someone about what you have been doing since the previous meeting) Check-in using Dixi Cards (with the group) Setting the scene – Introducing Systemisation of Experience (SoE) (GB – learning Community and our Transformational Stories) Sharing Learning Communities’ (LC) Participatory film	GB, GL Priya, AF
10.30	Break	

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

10.45	First Series of Questions – Reconstructing and reflecting on our LC experience	GB, AF
12.30	Lunch	
13.15	Second series of Questions – Learning experiences from participating in PLANET4B Research and being part of an LC	GB, AF
14.15	Break	
14.30	Third series of Questions – PLANET4B: Capturing and Exploring Stories of Change	GB, AF
15.30	Break	
15.45	Summary of Journey	AF
16:15	Participatory Film and Feedback	GB
16:35	What Next for the LC	GB, GL
16:45	Presentation of certificates	GB, GL
18.00	Shared meal	

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

Learning Community Participation in Workshop 5

At the outset of the project, the Learning Community (LC) committed to participating in four face-to-face workshops and one introductory online session. As the project evolved, participant feedback highlighted a strong interest in deeper engagement. As a result, the fieldwork schedule was expanded to include two additional online sessions and a fifth in-person workshop. The extra sessions created valuable opportunities for ongoing reflection, knowledge exchange, and connection among participants, aligning with the LC’s expressed desire to sustain the conversation and the research team’s aim to build a more cohesive learning experience.

The UK case study LC includes 11 participants from ethnic minority backgrounds, all of whom had previously participated in walks organised by Dadima’s CIC (DC). Geeta Ludhra (GL) and Subash Ludhra (SL), both walk leaders, play a dual role in the project — taking part as members of the LC while also helping to co-facilitate sessions alongside the Coventry University (CU) team. In total, 13 people are involved in the LC, including the walk leaders.

None of the participants identifies as having a disability.

Non-dependent children: over 16

Dependent children: under 16 or aged 16-18 and in full time education

Other multi-person household: flat shares, single parents with non-dependent children only, households containing more than one couple or single parent.

PLANET4B receives funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government’s Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government’s Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

Twelve members of the **LC** attended Workshop 5, a residential workshop held at the Mercure Hotel in Oxfordshire, England. This was the second overnight residential event for the LC. The workshop was organised around an activity called the Systemisation of Experience (SoE) and was designed to deepen engagement and foster a sense of connection and continuity. Only one LC member was unable to attend Workshop 5, due to personal reasons. Two members shared that they had declined invitations to family events to prioritise attending the workshop, reflecting their strong commitment to the LC. Additionally, two guests were present but did not formally participate in the workshop. One of these guests — the mother of a LC member — attended to support her daughter, a new mother, by caring for her baby and enabling her full participation in the activities.

The group spoke positively about attending the fifth and final workshop, highlighting that they enjoyed being part of an LC, valued the opportunity to reflect and learn together, and felt they had formed new friendships through the process. Participants particularly appreciated having a safe, supportive space to share their experiences and perspectives openly. One member captured the spirit of the group when they reflected on how the experience had shaped their thinking and connections, saying during Workshop 5:

I'm not missing this for anything because it's our last workshop, but it's also so special, and so we had that conversation... I think the community is what brought us really close together.

Their words echoed sentiments shared by many in the group, illustrating how the LC fostered both personal growth and a sense of belonging. The data, as detailed below, also illuminates that it inspired members to carry their learning forward into other areas of their lives.

Background and Context for Workshop 5

Systematisation of Experiences: A Learning Approach

The fifth workshop was intentionally designed around a *Systematisation of Experience* (SoE) framework, aimed at capturing the LC's collective journey through the PLANET4B project. This approach invited participants to reflect on, share, and critically reinterpret their personal and group experiences of involvement in LC workshops. At its core, SoE is a narrative reconstruction process — encouraging individuals to

PLANET4B receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

recount their engagement with the LC while exploring how this participation may have influenced their daily lives or inspired future action. Central to the process was the recognition of the LC's diverse perspectives and the depth of knowledge the individual members brought. To facilitate meaningful engagement, the fifth workshop incorporated a range of creative and deliberative methods designed to surface insights, encourage dialogue, and deepen understanding of participants' roles and reflections within the project.

Session Preparation

Before attending Workshop 5, preparatory activities were suggested to LC participants. They were invited to contribute to a shared LC Spotify playlist by choosing a song that conveyed a message about diversity, nature, change, or simply a song they loved. This activity aimed to promote self-expression, celebrate individual and collective identities, and encourage LC members to think about their experiences of PLANET4B through the medium of music. Participants shared their song choices, along with a brief rationale for their selection(s), in the LC **WhatsApp group**. SL volunteered to compile the song titles, create the playlist, share it with the Learning Community, and play the collection during Workshop 5 as a backdrop to reflection and conversation during breaks.

Link to [PLANET4B Spotify Play list](#)

Fragile by STING

I recently heard Fragile by Sting and had me thinking again of nature emotions/ human's impact all around and humans healing from nature. If that is eroded, how does it affect us?

Native Prayer

This is my song choice – when I listen to this, I go into a meditative state connecting to myself and ultimately to nature, Mother Earth and oneness.

What a wonderful World - Louis Armstrong

This is my song which kept me smiling through my childhood...colours of rainbow...so pretty in the sky...when I was lying in a field as a child I love and still love looking at the sky

Alongside the compiling of the playlist, a **short film** visually documenting the journey of the **LC** was also created (by **GB**), using images captured throughout the project. The film was shared with members of the LC via the project **WhatsApp group**, serving

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

as both a **reflection tool** and a **memory prompt** ahead of the workshop. It aimed to evoke shared moments, rekindle connections, and help participants prepare for deeper reflection on their experiences during our time together.

[Watch the short film on YouTube](#)

As an additional preparatory step, three posters were designed to refresh the memories of LC members and encourage reflection on the LC journey on PLANET4B. The posters feature images of workshops and serve as reminders of the various activities and methods used.

PLANET 4B UK CASE STUDY: WORKSHOPS DELIVERED			METHODS: ACROSS WORKSHOPS, WE HAVE USED SEVERAL METHODS TO EXPLORE OUR VIEWS AND EXPERIENCES ABOUT NATURE AND BIODIVERSITY		ACTIVITIES <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actor/Co-opp Uta • Nature Games • Photographic • Walking to Clays • Walks in the Clatters • Nature Challenge for children • Identifying local trees • Sharing nature photographs and stories via WHATSAPP
Invitation to Planet 4b: participating in a learning community 	Workshops 2 Sunday 7th April - 8 LC participants 	Workshops 3 Sunday 30th March - 10 LC Participants 			
Workshop 1 Sunday 4th February - 7 LC participants 	Online Participatory filmmaking meeting 	Workshop 4 Saturday 14th September - 9 LC participants 			

The final task, in preparation for the workshop, was for LC members to identify and bring an artefact that symbolises change. The plan was for LC members to come prepared to share with the group the reason for their choice of artefact and how it symbolised change.

It was expected that preparing for the fifth workshop in these ways would lead to deeper insights during the meeting, and in turn, to identifying transformational possibilities and personal stories of change.

Welcome and Introductions

GL and GB welcomed everyone to the workshop.

PLANET4B receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

Method and Facilitation

The workshop started with three icebreakers and sharing activities:

- **Activity 1:** This was led by a member of the LC who selected an oil and gave participants a paper leaf to write a word that came to mind when they smelled the scent.

The second activity aimed to encourage the LC to share their feelings about the day and/or their general outlook. Using Dixit cards with individual images, the LC was asked to select the image that best represented how they were feeling.

The third activity focused on a more in-depth introduction to the SoE and the development of our transformational story.

PLANET4B receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

Background to Systematisation of Experience?

- Popular culture intensified with the emergence of popular movements and organisations that questioned the imperialist and colonialist character of capitalism in Latin America.
- The methodology arose from social, political, educational, ecclesial, communicative, investigative, intellectual and cultural fields, identifying a necessity of co-producing systematic knowledge.
- In this context of reflection, systematisation of experiences is considered a legacy of popular education for the field of participatory research; it is a process of reflective practice (Torres 2010).

GB provided a brief overview of the SoE approach and outlined how participants could engage in reflection and share their thoughts throughout the day. A variety of methods were introduced to support this process, including posters, flip-chart paper, a reflection tree, group discussions, and interactive activities — each designed to encourage meaningful participation and capture diverse forms of insight and expression. To formally start the SoE process, the film (created by GB, also shared on the WhatsApp group in preparation for the meeting) capturing the group's engagement over the project duration, was shown, to jog memories further and highlight shared moments.

The day began by setting the stage for engaging in an SoE process and a series of rich conversations. LC members shared stories from the past, expressed hopes for the future, and

PLANET4B receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

reflected on what they valued about being part of PLANET4B. Discussions highlighted their sense of belonging to the LC, the joy of exchanging nature stories, and reflections on biodiversity and its significance in their lives. The data captured provided evidence of the emotional, practical, and knowledge-based benefits experienced by participants through their involvement.

The group has empowered me to make informed choices

...I didn't think I knew enough about biodiversity and therefore, really it was a fantastic opportunity that I was invited by [names Dadima's lead] to come.

First series of SoE Questions: Reconstructing and reflecting on our Learning Community experience

SoE Activity 1 aimed to encourage the LC to reflect on their motivations for joining the PLANET4B project and their experiences of participating in an LC. Participants were invited to consider a set of guiding questions:

- What were your initial thoughts about joining an LC?
- Why did you decide to participate?
- How do you feel about the relationship between being part of an LC and engaging in a research project exploring biodiversity?

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

- Did you experience any challenges in being part of the LC and/or engaging in this research?
- What has been your standout learning moment or activity?

Method and Facilitation

SoE Activity 1 was structured into three reflective stages:

Individual Reflection (10 minutes):

LC members considered the questions independently, using a variety of materials provided — paper leaves, flip chart sheets, notepads, or post it notes — to record their thoughts.

Paired Discussion (20 minutes):

Participants then shared their reflections in pairs, allowing for deeper dialogue and exchange of perspectives.

Group Dialogue (Facilitated by GB):

The final stage brought everyone together in a facilitated group discussion, providing space to surface common themes, share personal insights, and build collective understanding.

This activity led to a rich and personal discussion, during which LC members reflected on their experiences of being part of the group. Reasons for joining the learning community varied, however a key motivation was having received the invitation from Dadima's and being curious about engaging in a research study and learning about biodiversity.

I was curious ...I never really used it [biodiversity] in everyday conversation, but you know, it's become more of a word that I now understand better, and that's probably thanks to Dadima's quite significant influence.

During the activity, participants emphasised the value of safe spaces that facilitate the open sharing of personal stories and the discussion of difficult, often hidden experiences. They emphasised how important it was to speak candidly about their ethnic identities, recount experiences of racism and prejudice, and feel that their perspectives were genuinely heard and respected. The group described a sense of belonging that allowed them to explore topics they often find challenging to address in

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

other contexts. The accompanying image reflects these shared experiences, illustrating the impact of being part of a group where such dialogue is welcomed and supported.

Engagement in the LC was universally reported to have been experienced by participants as a means of centring conversations about nature, but also a space in which biodiversity - a term that many at the start of the project found difficult to define or rarely used - became normalised. Whilst there was acceptance that the project was only a start of engaging, one participant noted how they, nevertheless, would still have liked to learn more during the sessions:

It's been a very positive experience, but. I was hoping to get to know more about it, but I always said I'm still confused...

Nonetheless, a common theme among the group was that involvement led to an increase in confidence, a desire to learn more about biodiversity, and an empowering experience.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

Nature brands often white models	Books poetry nature – pushed me to reading decolonial scholar narratives.	Even if we are not scientific, we have something to say	Empowered knowledge
Being part of LC increases confidence	Spurs me on to do something else.	In trustee roles / the only person of colour in that role	Leading equity stand.
Language can be we're done to, but we have a rich history of biodiversity.	Our stories matter	Get wet, get cold	Some family members discourage
Previously, not many from minority backgrounds in nature	Being part of Dadima's	Talking to people from all walks of life doing their thing / Changing strangers' minds sometimes is easier than family.	You're being disruptive.

Alongside their interest in learning more about biodiversity, participants expressed a strong sense of connection with the LC group and process, which in turn catalysed action. This supportive environment gave members the confidence to take new steps or build on existing actions they were already undertaking.

I wouldn't normally speak in a group, but this felt welcoming— I felt heard

Several participants described feeling empowered and motivated to contribute to biodiversity efforts — even in small, personal ways — such as starting conversations or initiating activities within their families, friendship groups, and local networks.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

Key learning from First Series of SoE Questions

On reflection, across the data we see how the LC offered more than just an introduction to biodiversity — it built trust, a sense of belonging, and open conversation on complex and personal issues.

I just feel as though anything that you contribute is validating and ... you're not looked at with weird eyes... It felt like a space where no question was too small or too big — everyone listened and added their own thoughts.

Another reflected,

Hearing different perspectives helped me think about my own habits and how I could make small changes.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

While knowledge and confidence about biodiversity developed at different rates for participants, the group's safe and supportive environment encouraged both learning and action. Even small, personal steps taken outside the group demonstrate the long-lasting impact of creating spaces where people feel heard, valued, and inspired to contribute.

Second series of SoE questions: Learning experiences from participating in PLANET4B Research and being part of a Learning Community exploring issues associated with nature and biodiversity

The second series of questions posed during SoE Activity 2 aimed to explore the LC participants' reflections on engaging in a project centred around nature, the environment and specifically issues related to biodiversity and biodiversity loss. The discussion focused on what participants had learned, whether their perspectives had shifted, and if any changes had occurred as a result of their involvement in the PLANET4B project. While we were particularly interested in capturing the relationship between engagement in the workshop and biodiversity, we also allowed for some flexibility in our approach, remaining open to exploring broader issues associated with nature, the outdoors, and environmental practices.

Participants were invited to reflect on and discuss the following guiding questions:

- How do you feel about biodiversity now?
- Has engaging with others and being part of a community been a valuable tool for expanding your environmental interests and/or concerns beyond the LC? If so, how?
- Which method or activity has been most helpful in encouraging you to think more deeply about nature, biodiversity, or the environment more broadly?

Method and Facilitation:

PLANET4B receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

To explore these themes, a **World Café method** was employed. Three tables were set up, each equipped with flip-chart paper, Post-it Notes, and a dedicated facilitator — AF, BS, and LB — to guide the conversations and help capture key points shared by participants.

Members of the LC rotated between tables, spending 15 minutes at each station to reflect on the guiding questions and engage in small-group discussion. The CU research team also audio-recorded the discussions to ensure that all contributions were captured, allowing for further analysis and reflection.

The World Café activity created an open and inclusive environment for collaborative learning, enabling participants to explore diverse viewpoints and build upon one another’s insights. The activity encouraged the LC to share both personal reflections and collective learning.

Interviews and data from SoE Activity 2 revealed that, although some participants had prior understanding, many originally had limited engagement with or familiarity regarding the concept of biodiversity. For some, the term itself was entirely new and not part of their everyday vocabulary. One participant reflected that she “had no idea what biodiversity was”, initially associating it only with plants before realising the breadth and extent of its meaning:

You know what? I didn't even know the word. ...I'm not gonna lie to you. I had no idea what biodiversity was. I...But biodiversity was like, what are we going to do on that? What's that about? Yes, it's about the diversity of different plants and everything else that we have that

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

makes up our world, really, you know about humans, nature, plants, bacteria, didn't think of it like that ...

Overall, as highlighted in the table below, prior to joining the LC biodiversity was something most of the group gave limited consideration, with it commonly viewed as a term belonging to the scientific or academic community.

How did you feel about biodiversity at the start?

Not integrated into everyday life. The term is misunderstood. Doesn't make sense for different communities	I asked how does it relate to me. What could I do	Lost knowledge	The word was undefined – it was unclear. Unlinked to environmental concerns	An important thing. Key Driver. Didn't have sufficient information to understand
Strong understanding because of my profession. Wanted to understand how people of colour understood biodiversity	Had come across the term. Topical- Important. Felt uninformed about biodiversity	Knew about it. Now a deeper understanding through the exercises and walks	Clueless. Nothing. Hopeless. A pseudoscience. Meaningless word. Intimidating	Barriers. Time. Knowledge. Imposter Syndrome. Unequipped
Related to biological organisms. Science. Hard Facts. Data	Linked to farming, nature, flowers. Unlinked to walks and everyday experiences	A word that belongs to experts, Academics. I needed to know its importance, but it needs too much time.	Associating biodiversity with nature and food. Low-level understanding. More simplistic	Good idea of what biodiversity is through home education of daughter
Curiosity, optimistic, excited, curious	Some idea of meaning. The environment linked to climate change	Curious about the term. Understanding that things are linked	Not 'inside' but 'out there' in the Chilterns. High-level ecosystem understanding	

The reflections from the second series of (SoE activity 2) questions suggest a notable positive shift within the LC. Throughout the workshops, the term biodiversity became normalised and embedded in regular discussions about nature. Some participants broadened their understanding to encompass the diversity of all living things, while others reinforced or validated their existing knowledge and actions.

Participants began making tangible connections between biodiversity and their own lives, with engagement evolving from passive curiosity to active interest. This included a stronger desire to learn more and to integrate biodiversity considerations into personal decisions.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

Across the group, there was a notable increase in confidence when discussing biodiversity, indicating both a deeper understanding and a greater sense of ownership over the concept. The table below shows how conversation evolved into a multifaceted discussion in which factors such as religion, family, consumption and the environment, and change formed part of the LC meaningfully connecting biodiversity to their everyday lives.

How do you feel about biodiversity now?

No change in feeling, but change in actions. Will carry on, changed food and travel.	Being able to communicate with people. Confidence. Still learning how to articulate around biodiversity.	Used the term now. Understand how it links with multiple factors. Now it's understood to be part of a complex system. Looking for places to make change	Now understand the impact. Feel positive that there is hope, and we can achieve bio abundance.	Power in numbers to create change. Cumulative acts give power to small changes. Requires compromise, sacrifice, and more decision-making
Feel less intimidated. Feel that there is a 'kindness' about it, which leads to compassion for all living things.	Biodiversity in relation to faith – rethinking this. Meditation started in the forest, so it links back. There is hope. Positive possibilities	Questions education. Where is the richest learning done? Raises questions around town planning and decision-making in public spaces	Opportunities – outdoor exercise groups, yoga. Has made the group think about other opportunities to engage with biodiversity	Raises questions around ageing and fragility. How to bring older people together with young people to talk about biodiversity
Workshops have shifted perceptions – no longer distant. Now it's in the home. More personal and intimate	Linked to the political. Seeing how biodiversity is linked to the wider socio-economic system. How politics impacts what comes into our cupboards	I got excited about the seasons – having the workshops in different seasons. Something positive in every season	Now, to make the steps hopeful that it is positive to make a change. A sense of agency. Glad I can make economic choices	As part of the project, it has brought the value of education and knowledge of alternative lifestyles. She has witnessed the changes in others.
	Lots of co-learning, so the review of small actions has been in the context of witnessing other people's actions and through conversations.	Not changed but cemented. Has been lovely to see other people change	Can elicit change in all the environments he comes in contact with. Small changes are all influential.	

SoE Activity 2 led to informative conversations that demonstrated an increased awareness and provided encouragement and validation for individual thoughts and actions. Most experiences of learning about biodiversity and engagement in PLANET4B were positive; however, two participants raised concerns about the importance of effective communication channels. While sharing their enjoyment of engaging in the LC and the learning opportunities it provided, they also felt that there was still a lack of clarity about how the data generated in the workshop would be integrated into the broader project and actions, beyond the UK case study. They emphasised the importance of maintaining communication about the work beyond the workshops.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

Which methods have been the most helpful for thinking about nature and biodiversity?

Waking together with prompts that shift attention to the environment around you, such as 'what is blue'.	Dixit cards	increases awareness of how spaces make me feel, how it impacts how I feel and sleep. Discussion in the group is making me more aware of the need for more fresh air and less noise.	Creative writing group	Better understanding of what happens to our bodies, minds, senses, and emotions when spending time in nature, rather than artificial spaces.	Critical reflection
Family-oriented nature of the learning community	Dadimas meadow walk	Time walking in nature	Having a small group	Follow-up trip to Brom sea Island after workshop four, further extended the impact of the	Dadima's walks have been more about dwelling in the places rather than a mission destruction focus. It is also combined with the educational dimension, resulting in a very knowledgeable group.
Speaking with family members about the issues raises. The workshops also raises their awareness.	Nature podcasts	Slow methods that allow us to pause and think	Creating space for the cultivation of queries	Developing my garden alongside the learning community meetings, reading and learning	In-person meetings - Pushing back against the fact that everything is online
Activities that were small and with easy steps	Meditation	Significance of simply being able to talk and share about biodiversity – relating to nature	Biodiversity in the cupboard	The whole learning process dimension of the group	

Third series of SoE questions: PLANET4B: Capturing and Exploring Stories of Change using an artefact

This activity aimed to capture stories about change.

Methods

In preparation for the SoE Activity 3 session, LC members were asked to bring an artefact to prompt reflection and discussion about change. During this session they were invited to show their artefact, share why they chose it, and explain how it represented change.

PLANET4B receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

Use of Artefacts as a Catalyst for Reflection and Dialogue

The use of an artefact proved to be an effective and engaging method for LC members, enabling them to link their everyday experiences with stories of change. By anchoring abstract ideas in tangible, personal objects, the approach created an accessible entry point for reflection and discussion.

One participant, for example, shared that since joining the LC, he had begun to think more intentionally about the changes in his life and the world around him. The process

PLANET4B receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

of connecting his artefact to these reflections sparked rich conversations within the group, inspiring others to share their perspectives and experiences.

A little bit of a story. I gifted this to myself. It's a bamboo cup which I know this sounds like it could be any bamboo cup, but bamboo and I've sort of gone off and done a little bit of research about bamboo because it's one of the fastest-growing plants on Earth. So, with species growing up to 91 centimetres per day, it's extremely sustainable, and it's also really hard-wearing; it cleans really easily. I pop it in the dishwasher and I don't have any sort of issues ...It's also really biodegradableBeing part of this group has made me think about plastics more. I was saying to somebody earlier on about, you know, the drinking water and microplastics and water and what that does for the environment. Well, unlike plastic, which can take years to decompose and by the variable costs that many microplastics leave behind them ... really interesting thing, I learned is that bamboo can be harvested without killing the plant as it regrows from its root system.

This example shows how the artefact method encouraged participants to connect biodiversity and environmental issues to their personal lives. It also surfaced the values, emotions, and motivations that drive individual and collective action. By fostering deeper engagement, artefacts became powerful catalysts for both personal insight and group dialogue. Within this LC they helped members identify small actions already taken as a result of their involvement, as well as consider new actions they might pursue individually, within their families, and in their broader communities.

These workshops have just really consolidated where we're going and how we want to live our lives. I've just been zoned. ...we're heading towards a small holding, which is, you know, all about the land, and that's kind of where our life is going.

For another participant, her involvement with the LC was an essential aspect of encouraging her to develop the garden at her new home:

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

...you've seen the garden at the beginning, and you've seen the garden in October. At this precise moment, it's not very different from October, but in three weeks' time it will be very different, and I will post an update when everything starts blooming. But I just think it's a metaphor for the change that I've had in myself from these tiny little plants. ... I knew a bit about biodiversity and stuff... But it's the group, it's the change, how I've blossomed with everyone's help and knowledge and learning little tidbits from everyone and also then practical change which I just mentioned in the last group, that as a result it's important that we pass this on to the next generation. And I'm thinking of being part of a group that explains, in our local school, about biodiversity and connecting with nature. So that is something I hope to do from autumn onwards.

The second phase of discussion during SoE Activity 3 invited participants to reflect on how engaging in the research process — through attending workshops, experimenting with different methods, sharing information, stories, and photographs via WhatsApp, and participating in follow-up discussions during subgroup meetings or DC's walk series — had impacted their knowledge and perspectives on nature and biodiversity. Participants also explored how they might deepen or expand these changes moving forward.

Guiding questions encouraged LC members to consider whether participating in the study had prompted reflection on their values, cultural heritage, life experiences, and priorities concerning biodiversity; also, how they might or had incorporated shifts into their everyday lives. Participants were invited to share the most transformative insight or experience gained from participating in the LC, and how it would continue to influence their future decisions. These prompts surfaced further stories of change across individual, family, and community levels.

One participant, for example, described how discussions within the LC had prompted him to introduce a new recycling initiative into his family business:

...within our work within our warehouse, we've now implemented a recycling policy for our printer cartridges. We never used to recycle them, but now we've set that programme up, and that is on the back of obviously conversations we're having here. So, I think the key for me has been noticing, and then noticing where changes can occur.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

This example illustrates how involvement in the LC not only sparked individual awareness but also translated into tangible, practical action with a broader, lasting impact.

Categorising Stories of Change

The table below highlights how the stories of change reported by LC members can be grouped into three distinct but often overlapping levels:

- **Practical** – tangible actions and behaviours adopted in daily life.
- **Mindset and Values** – shifts in thinking, priorities, and personal connection to biodiversity.
- **Wider Social Effect** – changes that influence the wider circles in which members are situated, including families, workplaces, and communities.

These categories illustrate the breadth of impact, from small, individual lifestyle changes to broader ripple effects that extend beyond the individual.

Type	Examples reported	Impact
Practical Action	Seasonal eating, waste reduction, growing vegetables, gardening, organising time in nature, joining Bird Trust, consumption and purchasing patterns, shopping.	Direct environmental benefit, Model behaviour for others.
Mindset/Value Shift	Seeing biodiversity as part of everyday life, valuing small changes, and realising the interconnectedness of nature and people.	Sustains motivation, reframes daily choices.
Social Ripple Effect	Talking and inspiring children, family members, work colleagues to connect and see nature around them / value nature and engage with nature	Expands the reach of change beyond participant.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

Activity 4: Transformational stories: Summary of Journey and Next Steps

This activity was designed to encourage deep reflection on the theme of 'change' — broadly understood to include shifts in awareness, understanding, behaviour, and emotional or cultural perspectives. We were particularly interested in how members of the LC articulated their individual experiences of change — whether conceptual, practical, or aspirational — and the challenges or limitations they may feel in creating change in their own lives or communities.

Participants were invited to consider the following questions:

- **Reflecting on your experience and the idea of 'change':** How has engaging in research — through workshops, various creative methods, WhatsApp exchanges, subgroup meetings, and Dadima's walk series — impacted your knowledge or perspective on nature and biodiversity? How might you continue to build on these reflections moving forward?
- **Has being involved in this study prompted you to reflect on your values, cultural heritage, life experiences, and priorities related to biodiversity?** If so, how might this shift influence your day-to-day life?
- **What was the most transformative insight or experience you gained from participating in the LC?** How do you envision this shaping your future decisions or actions?

Activity 5: Our Journey and Next Steps

Discussion about the Participatory film

PLANET 4B - new

PLANET4B receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

One of the key outputs of the project will be a film developed with the LC outlining the central messages arising from the work. The film includes, photographs, video clips, and key messages generated and shared by the LC working with the CU team and an independent film maker. Workshop 5 offered an opportunity to share the latest version of the film with members, gather feedback, and make final adjustments. Creating the film has been a collaborative journey, with the LC eager to ensure that the messages they wish to communicate to policymakers remain central to the narrative. While the process has been lengthy and has highlighted some of the challenges associated with this method, it has also underscored the group’s commitment to accuracy and authenticity. During the discussion, members provided additional input on the film’s look, sound, and overall feel. It was agreed that CU would work with independent filmmaker Ben Cook to make the changes, and that the final version would be shared with the group via WhatsApp.

Discussion about the WhatsApp group

The WhatsApp group has been a valuable tool in strengthening relationships both within and between the LC and CU team. It offered an accessible, informal space for sharing knowledge, exchanging information, and posting content related to biodiversity, nature, and everyday life. The group included 18 members, and throughout the project, using Chat Stat, an AI-driven social media monitoring tool, we

PLANET4B receives funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government’s Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government’s Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

were able to demonstrate that it facilitated an estimated 2,768 individual interactions and the sharing of more than 2,773 images.

... having the WhatsApp group being so active as well in between the workshops, so that has been probably like the nicest .. most pleasant surprise.

While levels of engagement varied among participants, **all members of the LC actively contributed** to the WhatsApp group at some point during the project, highlighting its role in fostering a sense of **connection, continuity, and community**.

Using the software, we were also able to generate an A1 descriptor of the interactions within the group. For example:

A1 Assistant: Assistant: This WhatsApp conversation shows a group of individuals who are part of a learning community, likely focused on biodiversity and environmental conservation. They discuss various topics related to nature, including slugs, insects, the Northern Lights, nature markets, and the impact of the moon on wildlife.

The conversation includes sharing articles and links related to biodiversity, art exhibitions showcasing nature, and discussions about the upcoming residential workshop. There is also a sense of camaraderie and support among the members, as they wish each other well for festivals like Diwali and share personal updates.

There is a strong focus on learning and sharing knowledge within the group, as seen in the sharing of research reports, articles, and information about plants

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

and trees. Overall, the conversation reflects a passionate and engaged group of individuals who are dedicated to environmental issues and biodiversity conservation.

The LC decided that they would like the WhatsApp group to continue as a way of staying connected. It was agreed, however, that members should feel free to mute or leave the group if they wished, ensuring that participation remained entirely optional.

Presentation and a big ‘Thank You!’

The final formal activity offered a heartfelt opportunity for the research team to express their gratitude to the LC for their time, openness, and commitment throughout the project. In recognition of their contributions, each member was presented with a framed collage of images capturing their journey — a visual story of the moments, discussions, and connections that shaped their experience. This gesture celebrated not only the knowledge shared and the actions taken, but also the trust, relationships, and sense of collective achievement that had grown within the group. It marked a fitting conclusion to the project, honouring both the personal and shared impact of their journey together.

PLANET4B receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

Learning Community Social events

One of the most valued outcomes of the LC has been the genuine friendships that have grown through the research process. Workshop 5 included two social activities that provided members with the opportunity to share stories and enjoy each other's company. A group dinner was organised at the end of Day 1, where the laughter flowed as easily as the conversation, and LC family members were also invited to join the celebration.

The second activity was an optional morning walk the following day, offering a peaceful start to the day and a chance for more informal conversations. Strolling together in the fresh air, LC members continued to share ideas, reflect on the workshop, and enjoy one another's company.

PLANET4B receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

PLANET4B

ⁱ Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic communities or 'BAME' is frequently used to group all ethnic minorities. The term can disguise differences in outcomes between ethnic groups. Many ethnic minorities themselves say they do not like the term 'BAME', a finding reinforced by recent research commissioned by the [Cabinet Office Race Disparity Unit \(RDU\)](#)

PLANET4B receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.